

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidative regeneration of carbonyl compounds from oximes by quinolinium fluorochromate

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The oxidative deoxygenation of several aldo- and keto-oximes by quinolinium fluorochromate (QFC) in dimethylsulfoxide, exhibited a first order dependence on both the oxime and QFC. The oxidation of ketoximes is slower than that of aldoximes. The rates of oxidation of aldoximes correlated well in terms of Pavelich-Taft dual substituent-parameter equation. The low positive value of polar reaction constant indicated a nucleophilic attack by a chromate-oxygen on the carbon. The reaction is subject to steric hindrance by the alkyl groups. The reaction of acetaldoxime has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect has been analyzed by multiparametric equations. A mechanism involving the formation of a cyclic intermediate, in the rate-determining step, has been proposed.

Regeneration of carbonyl compounds from its derivatives under mild conditions is an important process in synthetic organic chemistry. Several oxidative methods are available for deoxygenation¹. Quinolinium fluorochromate (QFC) has been reported as a mild and selective oxidizing reagent for the formation of carbonyl compounds from the corresponding alcohols². Only a few reports about the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of QFC are available in the literature³⁻⁵. There seems to be no report about the kinetics and mechanism of oxidative deoxygenation by a halochromate derivative. We report here the kinetics of the oxidative deoxygenation of several aldo- and keto-oximes by QFC in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO). Mechanistic aspects are discussed.

Results and Discussion

The analysis of products indicated the following overall reaction :

QFC undergoes a two-electron change, which is in accord our earlier observation with PFC⁶ and QFC³.

Rate laws : The reaction is first order with respect to QFC. The individual kinetic runs yielded linear ($r^2 > 0.995$) plots

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of acetaldoxime by QFC at 298 K

10^3 [QFC] mol dm ⁻³	[Oxime] mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ s ⁻¹
1.0	0.1	6.14
1.0	0.2	12.3
1.0	0.4	24.8
1.0	0.6	36.1
1.0	0.8	49.3
1.0	1.0	61.0
1.0	1.5	92.2
0.5	0.8	49.0
2.0	0.8	49.7
3.0	0.8	48.6
4.0	0.8	49.2
5.0	0.8	48.8

Table 2. Rate constant and activation parameters for the oxidation of oximes (R¹R²C=N-OH) by QFC

Substituent		$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
R ¹	R ²	288	298	308	318 K	kJ mol ⁻¹	J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	kJ mol ⁻¹
H	H	1240	1700	2330	3040	20.5 ± 0.2	-19 ± 1	77.4 ± 0.1
H	Me	37.2	61.5	97.8	155	33.6 ± 0.2	-17 ± 1	85.6 ± 0.1
H	Et	28.0	45.3	72.2	120	33.9 ± 0.9	-16 ± 3	86.3 ± 0.7
H	Pr	14.6	24.2	40.4	67.6	36.4 ± 0.6	-17 ± 2	87.9 ± 0.5
H	Pr ⁱ	11.3	17.5	28.8	47.2	33.9 ± 0.9	-184 ± 3	88.6 ± 0.8
H	CICH ₂	88.6	125	196	269	26.0 ± 0.9	-194 ± 3	83.8 ± 0.7
H	Ph	232	361	552	898	31.6 ± 0.9	-167 ± 3	81.2 ± 0.7
Me	Me	10.6	17.7	29.2	45.2	34.4 ± 0.3	-183 ± 1	88.7 ± 0.2
Me	Et	8.33	13.2	21.3	34.6	33.6 ± 0.7	-188 ± 2	89.4 ± 0.6
Et	Et	5.62	9.21	15.4	24.4	34.9 ± 0.4	-186 ± 1	90.3 ± 0.3
Me	Ph	3.23	5.25	8.20	14.0	34.6 ± 1.0	-192 ± 3	91.7 ± 0.7

between $\log [QFC]$ and time. Further, the values of k_{obs} do not depend on the initial concentration of QFC. The reaction exhibited a linear dependence on the concentration of the oximes (Table 1). A constancy in the values of k_2 at $61.3 \pm 0.8 \times 10^{-4}$ (where $k_2 = k_{obs} / [\text{oxime}]$) confirmed that the reaction is first order with respect to the oxime as well.

Effect of temperature : The rate constants were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2).

Effect of solvents : The oxidation of acetaldoxime was studied in nineteen different solvents. The choice of solvents was limited by the solubility of the reactants and the reaction of QFC with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the chosen solvents. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of solvent on the oxidation of acetaldoxime by QFC at 318 K

Solvent	$10^4 k_2$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	Solvent	$10^4 k_2$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
Chloroform	52.5	Toluene	7.59
1,2-Dichloroethane	40.7	Acetophenone	49.0
Dichloromethane	45.7	Tetrahydrofuran	13.5
DMSO	155	<i>t</i> -BuOH	21.9
Acetone	32.3	Dioxane	16.6
Dimethylformamide	77.6	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	7.94
Butanone	22.9	Acetic acid	31.0
Nitrobenzene	56.2	Ethyl acetate	12.6
Benzene	9.12	Carbon disulfide	3.31
Cyclohexane	0.60		

An isokinetic plot between enthalpies and entropies of activation of the oxidation of the eleven oximes is not linear ($r^2 = 0.1843$, $sd = 4.5$ and $\Psi = 0.86$). However, according to Exner,⁷ an isokinetic relationship between the calculated values of enthalpy and entropy of the reactions is often vitiated due to the errors inherent in their values. He devised an alternative procedure for the verification of isokinetic relationship. An Exner's plot⁷ between $\log k_2$ at 288 and at 318 K is linear ($r^2 = 0.9960$, slope = 0.911 ± 0.019). The value of the isokinetic temperature is 719 ± 46 K. A linear isokinetic relationship is a necessary condition for the validity of linear free energy relationships. It also implies that all reactions so correlated follow a similar mechanism⁷.

The rate constants, k_2 , of the oxidation of acetaldoxime in eighteen solvents (CS_2 was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (2) of Kamlet *et al.*⁸,

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (2)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α the hydrogen bond donor acidity and A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eqn. (2), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below [(3)–(6)] :

$$\log k_2 = -3.86 + 2.08 (\pm 0.20) \pi^* + 0.15 (\pm 0.16) \beta + 0.53 (\pm 0.16) \alpha \quad (3)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9037; \text{sd} = 0.18; n = 18; \Psi = 0.25$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.90 + 1.89 (\pm 0.25) \pi^* + 0.33 (\pm 0.20) \beta \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8247; \text{sd} = 0.24; n = 18; \Psi = 0.32$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.94 + 1.98 (\pm 0.25) \pi^* \quad (5)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7939; \text{sd} = 0.25; n = 18; \Psi = 0.34$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.93 + 0.67 (\pm 0.42) \beta \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1338; \text{sd} = 0.51; n = 18; \Psi = 0.81$$

Kamlet's⁸ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 90% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion⁹ the correlation is not even satisfactory (*cf.* eqn. 3). The major contribution is a solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 79% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analyzed in terms of Swain's equation¹⁰ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also (7),

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (7)$$

here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvents, B the cation-solvating power and C the intercept term. ($A + B$) is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analyzed in terms of eqn. (7), separately with A and B and with ($A + B$),

$$\log k_2 = 1.74 (\pm 0.03) A + 1.82 (\pm 0.02) B - 4.36 \quad (8)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9979; \text{sd} = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.03$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.48 (\pm 0.60) A - 3.11 \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.2631; \text{sd} = 0.49; n = 19; \Psi = 0.72$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.69 (\pm 0.31) B - 3.79 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.6385; \text{sd} = 0.34; n = 19; \Psi = 0.46$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.79 \pm 0.02 (A + B) - 3.64 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9973; \text{sd} = 0.03; n = 19; \Psi = 0.04$$

The rates of oxidation of acetaldehyde in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation (*cf.* eqn. 8) with both the anion- and cation-solvating powers playing almost equal role. However, individually A and B are able to account for only 26 and 64% of the data only. The solvent polarity, represented by ($A + B$), also exhibited an excellent correlation. In view of the fact that sol-

vent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 99% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not very significant ($r^2 = 0.5934$; $sd = 0.36$; $\Psi = 0.30$).

We could not find any report about the mechanism of the reaction between a C=N bond and a halochromate derivative. However, the reaction of alkenes with chromium(vi) has been well studied¹¹. Since, olefinic bonds are not usually subject to a nucleophilic attack, it has been suggested that in the alkene-chromate reaction, an organometallic derivative is formed initially¹¹. The organometallic derivative then changes to a chromium(iv) diester in the rate-determining step. However, carbon-nitrogen double bonds, being dipolar in nature, can be easily attacked by a nucleophile. The data in Table 2 show that the rate of oxidation of ketoximes is much less as compared to that of the aldoximes. The reason for the slower reaction of ketoximes must be steric. As the central carbon changes from a trigonal to a tetragonal state, the crowding around it increases. This increase in the steric crowding will be more in the case of ketoximes as compared to that in aldoximes. This observation is supported by the correlation analysis of the reactivity of the aliphatic aldoximes also. The rate of oxidation of the aliphatic aldehydes did not yield significant correlation separately with Taft's σ^* and E_s values [(12) and (13)] :

$$\log k_2 = 0.90 \pm 0.58 \sigma^* - 2.28 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.3725, \text{ sd} = 0.64, n = 6, \Psi = 0.73,$$

$$\text{Temp.} = 290 \text{ K}$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.08 \pm 0.19 E_s - 2.12 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8891, \text{ sd} = 0.27, n = 6, \Psi = 0.21,$$

$$\text{Temp.} = 298 \text{ K}$$

The rates were, therefore, correlated with Pavelich-Taft's¹² dual substituent-parameter equation (14),

$$\log k_2 = \rho^* \sigma^* + \delta E_s + \log k_0 \quad (14)$$

The rates exhibited excellent correlations in terms of the Pavelich-Taft equation (Table 4); the reaction constants are positive.

Table 4. Reaction constants for the oxidative deoxygenation of aliphatic aldoximes by QFC*

Temp. K	ρ^*	δ	R^2	sd	Ψ
288	0.56 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.02	0.9995	0.02	0.02
298	0.52 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.01	0.9989	0.01	0.02
308	0.50 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.01	0.9998	0.01	0.03
318	0.43 ± 0.01	0.88 ± 0.02	0.9998	0.02	0.03

*Number of compounds is 6.

The low positive polar reaction constant points to an almost cyclic transition state in which the formation of the bond between chromate-oxygen and the carbon is somewhat ahead of the formation of N-O bond. This supports a nucleophilic attack by a chromate-oxygen on the carbon. The positive steric reaction constant points to a steric hindrance by the substituents. Therefore, the following mechanism (Scheme 1) is proposed for the reaction. The mechanism is supported by the values of activation parameters also. The low values of enthalpy of activation indicate that the bond-cleavage and bond-formation are almost synchronous. The large negative entropies of activation support the formation of a rigid cyclic activated complex from two acyclic molecules.

The faster oxidation of benzaldoxime may be attributed to the resonance stabilization of the cyclic activated complex. The oxidation of acetophenoxime is much slower. This may well be due to steric hindrance by the bulky phenyl and methyl groups.

Scheme 1

Hydroxynitrene (N-OH) has been recently reported as a very reactive intermediate¹³.

Experimental

Oximes were prepared by the reported methods and their m.ps. were checked with the literature values. QFC was also prepared by the reported method². Solvents were purified by the usual procedure¹⁴.

Product analysis : The oxidation of the oximes results in the regeneration of the corresponding carbonyl compounds, as confirmed by TLC (eluent : CCl_4 / Et_2O). Isolation of the product was attempted in the oxidation of oximes of benzaldehyde and acetophenone. In a typical experiment, the oxime (0.2 mol) and QFC (0.02 mol) were dissolved in DMSO (50 ml) and allowed to stand for *ca.* 10 h for the completion of the reaction. Silica gel (5 g) was then added to the reaction mixture and the mixture stirred for 15 min¹⁵. It was then filtered and the solid residue washed with the solvent (2×15 ml). The solvent was removed on a rotary evaporator and the residue purified on a silica-gel column (eluent : CCl_4 / Et_2O). Evaporation of the solvent afforded

the pure carbonyl compound. Yields of benzaldehyde and aceto-phenone were 1.73 g (81%) and 2.14 g (89%), respectively. The presence of HNO₂ in completely reduced reaction mixtures was confirmed by a positive starch-iodide test¹⁶. The oxidation state of chromium in a completely reduced reaction mixture, as determined by an iodometric method, is 3.96 ± 0.06 .

Kinetics measurements : The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess ($\times 10$ or greater) of the oxime over QFC. The solvent was DMSO, unless mentioned otherwise. The reactions were studied at constant temperature (± 0.1 K). The reactions were followed, for up to 80% reaction, by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of QFC at 356 nm spectrophotometrically. The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) was evaluated from the linear least-squares plots of $\log [\text{QFC}]$ vs time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed the rate constants to be reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. We have used coefficient of determination (R^2 or r^2), standard deviation (sd) and Exner's⁹ parameter (Ψ) as the measures of goodness of fit.

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